

A Geographical Study of Shri Somnath Temple Prabhas Patan in Gujarat: Satisfaction Levels of Tourists

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Abstract

Religious tourism, a prominent segment of special interest tourism, involves followers of various faiths traveling to sacred sites. This form of tourism is among the earliest known, with roots stretching back to the dawn of human civilization. Historically, these holy destinations have not only enriched the cultural landscape but also played a crucial role in local economies, becoming central to regional marketing efforts. At its core, pilgrimage can be defined as travel undertaken for religious purposes. Since these journeys blend spiritual experiences with travel, it can be tempting to categorize all visits to sacred sites as religious tourism. Today, both religious and secular pilgrimages are witnessing resurgence globally, reflecting a renewed interest in spiritual and reflective travel experiences. Therefore, here an attempt has been made to assess the Satisfaction index of Shri Somnath temple in Prabhas Patan. The tourist's data analysis covers various facilities like theirthe Destination can be easily reached, Diversity of Religious attraction, Darshan, Food and Water, Shopping Facilities, Surrounding Environment, Safety, Transport, Parking. Their expenditure at Shri Somnath temple and also covered their satisfaction regarding facilities and destination which are helpful for further development and to find out suggestions to the problems.

Keywords: Religion, Tourism, Facilities, Pilgrimage, Satisfaction

Introduction

India is a secular country, where all the individuals have the right to practice the religion of his or her own choice. In India, there are number of religious places that individuals visit. The country has number of temples, mosques, churches and other religious places, associated with all the religions practiced within the country. Religious tourism is regarded as the most common form of tourism. The reason being, within the country, individuals possess strong religious perspectives that if they would make visits to certain religious places, their aspirations would get fulfilled and they will be able to provide solutions to their problems. Religion and pilgrimage tourism is primarily referred to the travel that takes place outside the usual

environment for religious purposes In India, there are numerous religious places all over the country that have interested individuals from not only within the country, but also other parts of the world. Religious tourism is divided into the following categories, pilgrimages, missionary travel, leisure vacations, faith-based cruising, crusades, conventions and rallies, retreats, monastery visits, guest stays, faith-based camps and religious tourist attractions (Diverse Beliefs, 2012).

In this paper, I discuss different ways in religious center of Shri Somnath temple in Prabhas Patan. I use religious tourism as a broad term that refers to patterns of travel where visitors fulfill religious and recreational needs by visiting places of religious importance and pilgrimage sites in contemporary societies (Timothy and Olsen, 2006; Strasberg, 2011) In religious tourism, the main resources for the physical and metaphysical experience of the visitors include places of worship, temples, shrines, churches and cathedrals, rituals, festivals, performances and events (Shackley, 2001; Rinschede, 1992)

Objective

1. To Study the Satisfaction level of tourist at Shri Somnath temple at Prabhas Patan.
2. To suggest significant Suggestions for the tourism development at Prabhas Patan.

Data Base

The present research paper is based on primary and secondary data.

A. Primary Data

The primary data collected through standard anthropological techniques such as questionnaire, interviews, spot observation and case history also.

B. Secondary data

The secondary data collected from District Gazetteer, Journals, Books, Temple Committee Report and Internet are also referred to get secondary information. The collected data analyzed with simple statistical methods and represent with suitable cartographic techniques.

Methodology

Here an attempt is made to assess the level of satisfaction of the tourist by noting their views about various facilities provided to them at the destination. The facilities included are, accommodation, transport, and opinion about the place, food, and behavior of the people, shopping, and personal safety. Taken their opinion about the facilities either of excellent, good, satisfactory and unsatisfactory. These factors views were collected. These views were converted into numerical values such as 10 to 12 for excellent, 7 to 9 for good, 4 to 6 for satisfactory and 1 to 3 for unsatisfactory. The factor wise average values are calculated categorical summing up the values given by the tourist and dividing the total number of the tourist who noted that category. These average, then it multiplied by respective frequencies would give total satisfaction, then it divided by the total frequencies for the respective factor would give the satisfaction index for that factor.

For that, the following formula is used.

$$St_i = \frac{\sum M_i N_i}{N}$$

Where, St_i = Satisfaction Index for the 'i'th factor.

M_i = Numerical values for particular level of satisfaction for the Ith factor

N_i = Number of respondents deriving the particular level of satisfaction for the Ith factor.

N = Total number of respondents for that factor for all level of satisfaction.

Then the ranks are given to these satisfaction indices and finally coefficient of variation of all factors is calculated to see the consistency of the tourist.

Study Area

Shri Somnath temple at Prabhas Patan in Gir District of Gujarat State, India and this is famous for the religious center is located Shri Somnath temple is a small town in southern coastal Gujarat, located right at the shores of the India Ocean. It is located and got its name near a famous Somnath temple, considered to be among 12 most important temples of Shiva. There are about 8,000 people living in the town, and it is a small

industrial community, with many of the residents working in the neighboring city of Veraval. The extent of study area is 20°90'58" North and 70°38'75" East. An annual fair takes place on the Mahashivrati.

Sources: <https://www.mapsofindia.com>

About Somnath Temple

The famous Somnath Temple is a very sacred Hindu pilgrimage site. It is dedicated to Lord Shiva and is considered to be one of the twelve "Jyotirlingas" (lighted lingas), which is a symbol of Lord Shiva. The temple of Somnath has existed since times immemorial and it is also mentioned in the oldest Holy Scriptures, Rig Veda. An interesting fact about Somnath temple is that though it has been destroyed a number of times; it has always been rebuilt.

It is said that the Somnath temple was built by the moon God himself in gold, then by the demon king Ravana in silver, in sandalwood by Lord Krishna and in stone by the one of the rulers of Gujarat, Bhimdeva. It is said that the moon was very proud because of his beauty. Angered by his arrogance, his father-in-law cursed him to decrease and ultimately vanish. He pleaded for mercy and then was told to worship Lord Shiva. His curse was removed partially and he thus built the temple for Lord Shiva.

The architecture of the present temple reflects the Chalukya style of construction. The intricate and flawless carvings speak volumes about the skilled artisans of Gujarat. An inscription on the Arrow Pillar on the sea protection wall states that there is no piece of land between the point where the temple stands and Antarctica. The first President of India, Dr. Rajendra Prasad commented that the Somnath temple symbolizes the fact that the power of creation is always more than the power of destruction.

Indicator Wise Level of Satisfaction

Levels of satisfaction are a state of mind and there is universally accepted tool to measure it. However, here an attempt has been made to assess the level of satisfaction regarding facilities at Somnath Temple at the

time of versus season by adopting satisfaction method. For this assessment schedule filled up from 80 Tourists came from different locations.

Table 1 Distribution of Respondents Satisfaction Level

Sr. No	Indicators	Excellent	Good	Satisfactory	Unsatisfactory	Total
1	The Destination can be easily reached	12	20	32	16	80
2	Diversity of Religious attraction	20	26	24	10	80
3	Darshan Facility	15	22	30	13	80
4	Food and Water	21	16	28	15	80
5	Overall cleanliness of the destination	17	23	25	15	80
6	The quality of the accommodation	24	27	18	11	80
7	Possibilities for Shopping	15	20	22	23	80
8	Personal Safety and Security	20	22	16	22	80
9	Surrounding Environment	18	23	26	13	80
10	Organization of the local transport	14	18	27	21	80
11	Parking Facility	24	22	20	14	80
12	Cultural Diversity	21	26	23	10	80
13	Average	18.42	22.08	24.25	15.25	80
14	Percentage	23.02	27.60	30.31	19.06	100

Source: Based on Fieldwork 2023

The total pilgrims interviewed 80 and they were distributed according to their views about the facilities provided at the destination for the ten indicators the four levels of satisfaction are categorized which are termed as excellent, good, satisfactory and unsatisfactory. It shows that facilities provided at the shri Somnath Temple are excellent for 23 percent Pilgrims, good for 27 percent Pilgrims, satisfactory for 23 percent Pilgrims and unsatisfactory for 10 percent Pilgrims. Therefore, the level of satisfaction of the pilgrims is very high.

Indicator Wise Average Values of Satisfaction

Indicator wise average values are calculated for the identification of levels of satisfaction of pilgrim tourist were asked to assign points out of 12 (maximum) for the particular level of satisfaction they derived from each indicator. To ensure uniformity a forced distribution of points was adopted for convenience, like 10 to 12 as excellent, 7 to 9 as good, 4 to 6 as satisfactory and 1 to 3 as unsatisfactory. The average values for different levels of satisfaction for the different indicators are shown in the following table.

Table 2 These Average Values are used to Calculate Satisfaction Indices

Sr. No	Indicators	Numerical Values			
		Excellent	Good	Satisfactory	Unsatisfactory
1	The Destination can be easily reached	10.7	7.8	4.6	1.7
2	Diversity of Religious attraction	10.9	7.9	4.7	2.3
3	Darshan Facility	10.8	7.9	5.0	2.1
4	Food and Water	11.0	7.7	4.5	2.0
5	Overall cleanliness of the destination	11.1	7.6	5.2	2.6
6	The quality of the accommodation	11.2	8.1	5.8	2.6
7	Possibilities for Shopping	11.0	7.7	4.6	2.1
8	Personal Safety and Security	11.1	7.6	4.7	2.3
9	Surrounding Environment	11.3	8.7	5.1	2.1
10	Organization of the local transport	11.0	5.8	6.1	1.5
11	Parking Facility	10.8	8.0	6.6	2.0
12	Cultural Diversity	11.0	8.1	5.6	2.2

Source: Based on field work data

The above table shows the average satisfaction for the facilities like The Destination can be easily reached, Diversity of Religious attraction, Darshan Facility, Food and Water, Overall cleanliness of the destination, The quality of the accommodation, Possibilities for Shopping, Personal Safety and Security, Surrounding Environment, Organization of the local transport, Parking Facility, and Cultural Diversity this Facility divided for excellent, good, satisfactory and unsatisfactory. Here, in general average value highest of excellent is 11.8 in Perking facility, Surrounding Environment for good is 8.7 and for satisfactory is 6.6 and Organization of the local transport in unsatisfactory it is 1.5.

Table 3 Indicator Wise Satisfaction Index and Rank

Sr. No	Indicators	Satisfaction Index	Rank
1	The Destination can be easily reached	5.7	8
2	Diversity of Religious attraction	7.0	4
3	Darshan Facility	6.4	6
4	Food and Water	6.4	6
5	Overall cleanliness of the destination	6.6	5
6	The quality of the accommodation	7.8	1
7	Possibilities for Shopping	5.9	7
8	Personal Safety and Security	6.4	6
9	Surrounding Environment	7.1	3
10	Organization of the local transport	5.7	8
11	Parking Facility	7.4	2
12	Cultural Diversity	7.4	2

Source: Based on field work data

The above table shows Indicator Wise Satisfaction Index and Rank of tourists concerning facilities. Tourists are more satisfied with the quality of the accommodation Facility first rank (7.8), Parking Facility and Cultural Diversity second rank (7.4) as well as Surrounding Environment third rank (7.1) Accommodation is first rank because a new construction in outside of the temple campus including with all facility related to accommodation. Second rank is Parking and cultural diversity because huge of parking area and all types vehicles park in basis of computer raised. This temple is mostly visited tourist in all religious that is this campus is showing the cultural diversity. This temple is situated in the near of the sea, that is Surrounding Environment most beautiful nature.

Fig. Indicator Wise Rank

Source: Based on field work data

Diversity of Religious attraction fourth rank (7.0), Overall cleanliness of the destination fifth rank (6.6). Darshan Facility as well Food and Water also Personal Safety and Security six ranks (6.4) for the reason that this temple is Hindu religious and considered to be among 12 most important temples of Shiva as well the temple of Somnath has existed since times immemorial and it is also mentioned in the oldest Holy Scriptures, Rig Veda. This temple committee has more careful in the cleanliness of the temple. Dardhan and food, water facility as well safety is very good viewed all is extra constantly in the temple of committee.

Possibilities for Shopping seen rank (5.9), this temple campus is more variety of shops but these goods are not cheap rate this reason shopping facility is seen rank given in the tourist. Last but not least the Destination can be easily reached and Organization of the local transports eight rank (5.7) for the reason that the destination not well connected to main road. Veraval to Somnath temple distance 8 km and Junagadh to Somnath temple distance 95 km these two cities are not well connected and not arrange the local transports.

Conclusion

Shri Somnath is one of the important religious center in Gujarat. The people from surrounding area are visiting of the famous Shir Somnath temple and attracts a good number of tourists due to a high popularity of local crafts, unique artistic dancing of the sasankathi in the surrounding of the temple. There is a lack of infrastructure like; accommodation Facility first rank, Parking Facility and Cultural Diversity second rank as well as Surrounding Environment third rank and other facility tourist are more satisfied.

If these problems will minimize and solved, this place can be developed very much from the pilgrimage tourism point of view.

Suggestions

1. The more of tourists are coming various region of the country to Shri Somnath temple but they are not getting proper darshan so this facility should be improved lanes should be maintained.
2. Tourist are waiting of local transportation in Shri Somnath temple to veraval and junagadh because lack of local transportation so should be pervading for more local and S.T bus the transportation all season in time to time.

3. Shri Somnath temple to all local road should be connected to paaka road in surrounding in the temple.
4. At the time of Shri Somnath Fair tourists faces the local transportation and other facility should be made available by nearest to the surrounding area of the temple.
5. At the time of Shri Somnath Fair shopping facilities should be improved Prizes should be equal because rates are not fixed, they should fix by temple committee.

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